

PERFORMANCE MANAGEMENT STRATEGIES: A PANACEA FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHERS SERVICE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

This paper x-rayed performance management strategies: panacea for teachers' service in secondary schools Nigeria. It saw performance management strategies as concerned with employees at work and spurring out the best in them for effective teacher services. These strategies are supervision, delegation, effective communication, collaboration and among others that are applied with the possession of sound knowledge for positive results. The paper went ahead to reveal the performance of Principals as a Panacea for Effective Teachers Services, asserting that a principal is the head administrator of a school. Also x-rayed in the paper are the constraints to performance management strategies which includes but not limited to lack of capacity, inadequate provision of financial and material resources, not recognizing and rewarding performance of school supervisors, principals and teachers irregularity and delay in payment of salaries. The paper concluded that performance, arguably, is a demonstrative act which embraces results as well as the effective use of appropriate skills, knowledge, competences and behaviours to achieve them. It is the seen output of educational officers in delivering the goals of education at all levels.

Keywords: Performance, Management, Strategies, Constraints, Teachers, Services.

Reference to this paper should be made as follows:

Kpenu, C. T., & Elemelu, C. (2026). Performance management strategies: A panacea for effective teachers service in secondary schools in Nigeria. *International Journal of Institutional Leadership, Policy and Management*, 8(2), 275-295. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.20820815>.

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INTRODUCTION

Educational institutions have been seen as an organization that demands a high level of management effectiveness in the actualization of its aims and objectives. Most times, these

educational institutions are unable to perform effectively in the attainment of the goals and objectives upon which they are set up. Education, sometimes experiences setbacks which may be due to failure to adopt effective performance strategies such as supervision, staff appraisal, effective communication, consultation, delegation, in-service training among others. Subsequently, they are unable to achieve stated goal and objectives of the school system. These strategies are regarded as systematic processes which facilitate the maximum achievement of the goal of the school system. Performance of the school as an organization can be enhanced to improve the performance of individuals within a team framework. It is a means for promoting superior performance by communicating expectations, defining roles within a required competence framework and establishing achievable benchmarks.

The value of performance management to the wellbeing of schools can be fully understood in the view of Aguinis (2009), who concurs with Armstrong (2006), and saw performance management as a continuous process of identifying, measuring and developing the performance of individuals and teams and aligning performance with the strategic goals of the organisation. The performance management strategies can be used to communicate organizational goals and objectives, reinforce individual accountability for meeting those goals, and track and evaluate individual and organizational performance outcome. It reflects a partnership in which managers share responsibility for developing their employees in such a way that enables employees to make effectual contributions to the organization. It is evidently a defined process for managing people that will result in success for both the individual employee and the organization.

The need for performance management strategies as an administrative tool for teachers services in public secondary schools cannot be overemphasized. This is because performance management strategies can be used for goal setting and to improve self-evaluation and appraisal. To improve effective performance at the secondary school level, personal experience has shown that some supervisors of schools, principals and teachers have outstanding roles to play in the attainment of institutional goals and objectives. This implies that performance management strategies if implemented in secondary schools will enable supervisors of schools, principals and teachers to evaluate individual or group performance. It will also help in optimizing productivity by providing visible and clear accountability related to performance expectation for effective goal attainment.

The aim of applying performance management strategies is to develop individuals with the required commitment and competencies for working towards the shared meaningful objectives within an organizational framework. This can be related to performance targets during a specific performance period from the supervisors or administrators. Goals on one hand motivate individuals to exert extra effort, to persist and focus attention on relevant task features. On the other hand, it directs behaviour of an individual or group and provides guidelines for how much effort is to be put into work performance for an expected result. Personal contact with some supervisors of schools, principals and teachers has shown that people are likely to perform better if they are convinced that they will be rewarded promptly and appropriately after evaluation and assessment. This implies that teachers services is necessary in order to identify the performance of an individual - what a staff should be doing and how he should be doing it, how long it should take and the things required for its accomplishment. However, for a reliable goal attainment, school administrators should adopt and apply effective performance management strategies to enhance smooth measurement, evaluation and appraisal of employees in public senior secondary schools.

Supervision is the act of monitoring the employees in an organization with the aim of assisting them to achieve the goal of the organization. Supervision includes conducting basic management skills (decision-making, problem solving, planning, delegation, and meeting management), organizing teams, noticing the need for and designing new jobs roles in the group, hiring new employees, training new employees, employees performance management (setting goals, observing and giving feedback, addressing performance, issues among others. It also involves ensuring performance to personnel issues policies and other internal regulations. In secondary school administration, the principals and supervisors from Education Schools Board have strong working knowledge of the activities of the school system. They know how to identify the teachers through the process of evaluation.

The aim of supervision is to monitor the performance of school staff and students, taking note of their strength, weakness all geared towards improving the standard of performance and also the teaching and learning environment for goal attainment. The concept of supervision is therefore, directed to the changing of the behaviour of staff for effective performance.

Effective communication is one of the strategies principals or administrators employ to boost the performance of teachers. It helps to understand each other in the line of executing or carrying out task as assigned. According to Graham and Lebron cited in Onogri (2009) posited that organizations have employ communication strategy to resolve conflict that ensued in the process of performing their duties. This is actualized or achieved by breaking down barriers or resistance among workers and promoting their trust and cooperation among them.

Communication is a rational process which involves initiating messages using symbols, signs to express meaning, create similar understanding and influence actions. It is a process or means by which information is shared among individuals through a common system of symbols, signs or behavior (Ololube, 2024). Appelbaum et al. in Ongori (2009) posited that groups in trying to actualize a common goal encounter internal and external problems which may reduce their performance, hence effective communication is needed for effective understanding that will promote high performance.

It is necessary to state that no positive action can occur in organization in the absence of effective communication. In order to achieve secondary education goals, principals must develop the right channel that will aid effective communication for efficient functioning of the school. Effective Communication is a strategy which allows free flow of information between superiors and their subordinates. It entails providing necessary and timely information to members of staff on issues, administrators adopting the right communication skill, not using abusive words, not attacking, not threatening or making accusation

Collaborative or consensus decision making style is a style of decision where by the administrator ask for the teams information, ideas, opinions and contributions either individually or collectively while he takes the final decision as an administrator (Stoner, 2018 in Ololube, 2018).The management group are involved in the decision-making in the organization and its implementation. In case of occurrences of any challenge emanating from the concluded decisions by the team or group, they collectively stand together to tackle the challenge believing they are the stakeholders in the organization (school). Collaboration of the administrators with the staff in decision making is very crucial as a performance strategy to achieve the goals of secondary education. According to Ololube (2024), collaborative decision making occur when the decision maker (administrator) make decision together with his staff. He further stated that if the staffs are expertise, he will be endowed with enough information from the staff.

A team of external supervisors from the Post Primary Schools Board (PPSB) visit each school periodically to monitor, inspect and supervise the school to ensure that the standard stipulated by the Ministry of Education are attained. The supervisors of schools, principals and teachers, in addition to their roles as supervisors and managers of the teaching and non-teaching staff, students and school activities, are saddled with the responsibility of educational management and administration. In fulfilling their role, they are called upon to perform a variety of tasks, most of which are related to student actions, curriculum development, community relations and performance management. As leaders of a group of teaching and non-teaching staff, the supervisors of schools have been conferred with the power to interact, communicate and supervise the activities of every principals and staff, principals the activities of teachers and students while teachers, the activities of students. The aim of such supervisory role is to improve their performance and stipulate standards for teachers' services in secondary schools.

Secondary education is a critical level of education in Nigeria's educational system. It represents the bedrock on which higher education is built and constitutes the foundation of whatever a student desires to become in life. However, it is sad to note that the performance management strategies applied at this level of education in Rivers State public senior secondary schools and Nigeria at large is insufficient. A number of reasons have been adduced as being responsible for this ugly trend that has affected attaining positive goals. On the part of the staff, lack of supervision, effective communication, non-payment of salaries and poor reward system by the government hinder the interest of staff in keeping up their performance whereas, on the part of the student, staffs have been blamed particularly for their failure to update and evaluate their knowledge on modern pedagogical strategies and skills with a consequent abysmal performance and poor goal attainment.

To correct this discrepancy, the introduction and sustenance of performance management strategies in public secondary schools becomes pertinent and indispensable. Performance management strategies according to Koko (2012) are systematic processes for improving an organizational performance by developing the performance of individuals and groups. Performance management strategies are based on the principle of management by agreement or contract rather than management by command. It involves managing, administering, measuring, assessing, evaluating and appraisal, effective communication, etc. This implies that a performance management strategy emphasizes the development and the imitation of self-managed learning plans as well as integration of individual and corporate objectives. It is concerned with provision of an integrated and coherent range of personnel management processes that are mutually supportive and contributing as a whole to improve organizational effectiveness for goal attainment.

Armstrong (2009) contended that performance management strategy is a process for establishing a shared understanding about what is to be achieved, how it is to be achieved and an approach of managing people to increase productivity by attaining a successful goal. The steps of performance management strategies are therefore effective supervision, job enrichment, measurement, recognizing, etc. among others and rewarding top performances, effective communication, establishing focus for skill development and control mechanism. If these aforementioned steps are applied in public secondary schools, it will enhance job performance for effective goal attainment.

These strategies however, when applied involve the process of supervision, inspection, staff appraisal and evaluation and are considered comprehensive and appropriate enough for administrators to assess, appraise and evaluate staff performance to achieve maximum

cooperation and result. It is the process through which various performance problems militating against attaining effective goals could be corrected and turned around.

But it is quite sad that some supervisors of schools, principals and teachers are yet to apply these strategies to improve performance standard. It is also sad that some supervisors of schools, principals and teachers encourage favoritism in measuring, assessing and evaluating staff and student's performance in public secondary schools. All these result in low performance and thereby desired goals are not achieved since the appropriate strategies are not applied. Hence, this paper examined performance management strategies: a panacea for effective teachers' service in secondary schools.

METHODOLOGY

This paper adopts a descriptive and analytical research design. The descriptive aspect focuses on outlining various performance management strategies, while the analytical aspect evaluates their effectiveness in improving teachers' service delivery. The paper relies on secondary data sources such as peer-reviewed journal articles, government reports, policy documents, and case studies from educational institutions. Scholarly databases such as Google Scholar, ResearchGate and academic repositories will be utilized to source relevant materials. Recent literatures published will be prioritized to ensure the inclusion of recent findings and trends in performance management strategies in education. The selection will focus on research addressing teacher evaluation, feedback mechanisms, professional development, motivation, and accountability frameworks. The paper will be guided by goal-setting theory and performance management theory to provide an in-depth understanding of how structured performance evaluation, incentives, and professional development contribute to effective teaching services.

A thematic analysis approach will be used to identify key themes in the literature related to performance management and teacher effectiveness. Findings will be synthesized to draw meaningful conclusions on best practices and policy recommendations. This paper focuses on public secondary school teachers, emphasizing performance management strategies applicable within this educational setting. However, it may not extensively cover performance management in private schools or higher education institutions. Since this study is based on secondary data, ethical considerations involve ensuring proper citation of sources, avoiding plagiarism, and maintaining academic integrity throughout the paper.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Chester Barnard's (1938) Efficiency and Effectiveness of Organization Theory cited in Johnnie (2019) states that the function of the chief executive of an organization is to ensure efficiency and effectiveness in the organization, efficiency being employee centered and effectiveness being employer and task oriented. The theory suggests that authority flows down but depends on acceptance by the subordinates. Barnard originated much of the behavioural science approach. O'Connor cited in Peretomode (2013) pointed out that Barnard had long said that managers need to know more about human behaviour, and in particular more about informal groups of an organization, especially the relationships between workers and outsiders. He stated that the willing of employees to accept authority depends on four conditions:

- Employees must understand what the manager wants them to do (employees must understand the communication).
- Employees must be able to comply with the directive. That is if they feel mentally and physically able to carry out the order.
- Employees must think that the directive is in keeping with organizational objectives.
- Employees must think that the directive is not contrary to their personal goals.

Barnard is probably best known for his concept of “zones of indifference” he believed that each person has a zone of indifference or a range within each individual in which he or she would willingly accept orders without consciously questioning authority. Ololube (2024) asserted that the chief executive of the organization will regulate how and even if employees will obey and work for the effectiveness of the organization by providing all necessities for optimum productivity. There are only three types of orders that can be given by managers to employees:

- First are orders that are unquestionably acceptable and that are always obeyed because they lie within what Barnard called their zone indifference, or typically dealt with things that are part of an employee’s job description and are routine.
- Second are orders that may or may not be followed, depending upon the employee and the conduct accepted by the employee’s informal organization because such orders come close to being unacceptable.
- Third are orders that are completely unacceptable and that will always be disobeyed because these kinds of orders go way beyond an employee’s zone of indifference (O’Connor, 2012:4).

The zone of indifference represent degree of freedom that provides significant direction for executives and the wider the zone, the greater flexibility of action they enjoy in furthering the work of the organization and the less time and energy they must spend justifying their decision or soliciting agreement.

The relevance of this theory to this study is that, school principals/managers in the course of carrying out their task to ensure effective performance of the staff under them should from time to time delegate duties, supervise teachers and ensure effective communication with them in order for them to be effective in their job performances to achieve educational goals and objectives. The school principals, who must be human in the discharge of his duties, must be aware of various human behaviours. The knowledge of these behaviours will enable him to see staff and students as fellow humans as he will equally collaborate with teachers for improved productivity.

However, it is evident from the theory that if management of any institution wants increased performance from her staff, their supervision, staff appraisal and effective communication, among others should be considered. In essence, the principal must be aware of the various management strategies and understand when to use any of them for effective goal attainment in secondary schools in Rivers state.

CONCEPTUAL REVIEW

Performance

What is actually meant by ‘performance’ is perhaps debatable and probably regarded differently in different contexts and among different occupational groups. A dictionary definition offers the following: the act or process of performing or carrying out; the execution or fulfilment of a duty; a person’s achievement under test conditions (Ololube, 2024). In one sense this refers to something accomplished: the outcomes or the outputs. However, performance is about doing the work as well as being about the results achieved. Performance encompasses behaviour and activity and the way individuals, teams and organisations carry out their work.

Management

Management and administration are frequently used synonymously. The efforts of scholars to define the concepts have ended up in listing all the activities that describe the functions of administrators or the managers. However management is more often used to describe industrial activities while administration is used to refer more to government business (Okoroma, 2006). This description of management and administration suggest a variety of styles of school management. Cole (2006) opined that management is derived from the word “to manage” which means “to handle, plan, coordinate, direct, organize, forecast, control and to carry out a purpose”. Cole however defines management as a process. This definition above implies that management can be referred to the controlling process in an organization like the secondary level of education in Nigeria.

In the words of Resser in Akilaiya (2008) management is the utilization of physical or material and human resources through cooperative effort accomplished by performing the functions of planning, staffing, organizing, directing, forecasting and controlling. He went further to explain that managers are saddled with the responsibility of setting goals and to ensure that the goals are attained (Akilaiya, 2008). From the foregoing, management could be seen as a collection of processes. These will include such things as setting a goal, working towards the process of attaining a goal, planning, supervision, assessment and evaluation. According to Umoh and Ekanem (2015) management could be seen as a discipline which to them simply means a field of study. This explanation defines the position of educational management in Nigerian educational system.

Educational management therefore is the arrangement of human and material resource programmes available for education and carefully using them systematically for the attainment of educational goals. According to Okoroma (2000) educational management or administration is the process of bringing men and materials together for effective and functional teaching and learning in school. It is a process concerned with using methods, principles and practices to establish, develop and execute the goals and objectives of education. However, the human resources are the key factors with which educational goals can be attained by applying the various performance management strategies.

Performance Management

Performance management is that part of management which is concerned with employees at work and their relationship within the educational enterprise and seeks to bring together and develop into an effective educational organization, men and women who make up the administrative and academic workforce, enabling each to make his or her contribution to its success. According to Armstrong (2009) performance management is a systematic process for improving organizational performance by developing the performance of individuals and teams. It is a means of getting better results by understanding and managing performance within an agreed framework of planned goals, standard and competency requirements. Agreeing with the above assertion Weiss and Hartle in Armstrong (2009) defined performance management as a process for establishing a shared understanding about what is to be achieved and how it is to be achieved, and an approach to managing people that increases the probability of achieving success. From the above definitions, performance management strategies refer to the processes and techniques employed by the employers to improve and bring the best input from the employees. In secondary school administration, the principals who is the chief administrator employs different strategies to spur the teachers to put in their best performance in attainment of the goal of the school.

Furthermore, it is concerned with inputs such as the knowledge skills and attitudes of staff and administration. This results into the output which is achieved by the end of the process. Performance management is also concerned with measuring these results and reviewing progress in the achievement of targets and striving for continuous improvement and continuous development by creating a learning culture. Performance management is a management concept that involves redesigning jobs so that they are more challenging to the employee and are less repetitive. In other words, it is a type of management design intended to reverse the effects of tasks that are repetitive requiring little autonomy. Nwabueze (2010) contended that the main concern of performance management is aligning individual objectives to organizational objectives and encouraging individuals to uphold corporate value. It is sometimes assumed that performance appraisal is the same thing as performance management. However, performance appraisal can be defined as the formal assessment and rating of individuals by their managers at or after a review meeting (Armstrong, 2009). In contrast, performance management is a continuous and much wider, more comprehensive and more natural expectations. It emphasizes the support role of managers who are expected to act as coaches rather than judges and focuses on the future.

The overall objectives of performance management according to Cole (2006) and Armstrong (2009) is to develop the capacity of people to meet and exceed expectations and to achieve their full potential to the benefit of themselves and the organization. Performance management provides the basis for self-development but importantly, it is also about ensuring that the support and guidance people need to develop and improve is readily available.

Performance Management Strategies

Strategies, according to Ololube (2024), are the means by which policy is implemented. Bush and Coleman (2000) opined that strategy is an overview of an organization which encompasses all its activities. Strategies used by principals or educational administrators within the context of this study are the various ways that principals used to implement policies in education effectively

and efficiently for teachers to be productive. As such Performance management, therefore, can on the one hand be seen as a mechanism of subjugation, stripping teachers of professional autonomy and imposing ever more sophisticated strategies of surveillance upon their work. On the other hand, performance management can be seen a means to prioritise the needs of learners and professional development by maximising the quality of teaching and removing incompetence whenever it is found.

Armstrong (2009) defined performance management strategies as a process which aims at providing more opportunities in job performance for some measure and assessment of personnel and group performance to attain set goal. Performance management strategies however is the process through which various problems militating against teachers services could be corrected and turned around. It is a way of motivating employees by giving them increased responsibility and variety in their jobs. The strategies involve performance planning, monitoring, joint goal setting, conducting a performance review meeting, reporting in form of feedback, rewarding good work, coaching (Armstrong, 2009). Koko (2012) opined that strategies of performance management involve inspections of individual, evaluating their performance and reporting in form of feedback mechanism. These strategies can only be achieved through effective supervision and inspection, monitoring, measurement, evaluation and staff appraisal of teaching and non-teaching staff in the school and can serve us control mechanisms.

Supervision as a Panacea for Effective Teachers Service

The term supervision is derived from the word “super video” meaning to oversee (Ololube, 2017). The aim of supervision is to monitor the performance of school staff and students, taking note of their strength, weakness all geared towards improving the standard of performance and also the teaching and learning environment for goal attainment. The concept of supervision is therefore, directed to the changing of the behaviour of staff for effective performance. Supervision is a process of stimulating growth and the means of helping teachers to help them.

Firz (2006) described supervision as a process of directing, helping, guiding and stimulating growth in the subordinates in order to improve the quality of instruction. Supervision involves providing expert assistance to teachers to help them acquire more skills and competencies for effective teaching. Normakoh (2019) is of the view that supervision intends to supervise, guide and direct the instructional activities of teachers in line with the professional conduct. From these definitions above, it can be deduced that the main center of focus of supervision is the classroom teacher who as a curriculum implementer, tries to shape the destiny of class instruction. To this end, it is a service rendered to teachers, focusing on how to help them understand and accept themselves, their abilities patterns of interest, emotional make-up and background preparation and helping them set realistic goals for themselves. The principals is saddled with this responsibility of provide expert assistance to the teachers in all areas of instruction due to his wealth of experience and trainings received continuously. Effective supervision tends to bring out the best in teachers and prepare them for future supervisory roles as well.

The reason for supervision is to assist staff to assess their work and performance with a view to reinforce effective pedagogical methods and appropriate remedial action where professional lapses have been observed to improve their performance for effective goal attainment (Ogbizo, 2011). Supervisors need to take initiative to assist a group to move towards productive goals that are acceptable to dispose needs of individuals within the groups. The

supervisor as an evaluator provides assistance to teachers in evaluation instruction and curriculum. The supervisor helps teachers to find answers to curriculum and instructional problems, evaluate their classroom performance, assess their own strength and weaknesses and select means of overcoming their deficiencies (Hoy & Forsyth in Obasi, et al., 2015).

Therefore, supervision can help staff of secondary schools to become focused, self-directed and competent in performing their task for goal attainment. It also involves guiding, coordinating and persuading staff to cultivate good working personal attitudes for the attainment of the set goals. To Normakoh (2019), supervision as a strategy for effective performance is geared towards strategies whether they fall in any of the above strata are specifically geared towards: Curriculum development, Teacher development, Students' academic performance and Administrative excellence. It therefore means that supervision is intended to spur high performance of staff. Stoner (2002) posited that the duties and responsibilities of principals has expanded further to include task areas like instructional supervision, communication, decision-making, provision of incentives for teachers and students, financial management, plant management, professional development, conflict resolution strategies, adherence to statutory regulations in school administration, public relations and utilization of ICT resources to meet global best practices. Thus, success in school management to increase students' achievement and inculcation of relevant skills and aptitudes for sustainable development is perceived to hinge upon principal's ability to effectively perform his duties within the context of these critical task areas.

Instructional supervision is a vital area in the management of secondary schools. Supervision of instruction is the process of ensuring that effective teaching and learning takes place in the school system (Watson & Ajekere, 2020). According to Ololube and Major (2014), supervision of instruction involves the school administrators' ability to effectively see that aspects of instructional delivery in the school system are properly carried out to enhance learning. Watson and Ajekere (2020) saw supervision as one of the indispensable task of an effective administrator in the operation of a good school system because in addition to arranging and organizing for effective teaching and learning to take place, the school head must undertake to supervise the instruction going on. It is the duty of the Principal to see that meaningful learning is taking place in all the classes and that the teachers are teaching what they are supposed to teach, and in a manner that the students understand and enjoy their lessons. This is because, the teacher plays a significant role in response of the need to employ curriculum in the direction of sustainable development. This is so because according to Oghiagbephan (2017), the teacher kindles the learners' interest during the instruction process to stimulate thinking, making learning enjoyable, exciting and concrete.

The essence of instructional supervision seems not to be achieved in most schools. The principal need to properly supervise instruction to ensure that teachers help formulate, shape, design and interpret curriculum programmes for optimal success. Effective supervision of instruction is lacking in most Nigerian secondary schools hence the perceived decrepitude in the standard of education. He emphasized that Nigerian society demands qualitative education to give the youth functional education, which cannot be achieved without effective supervision of instruction to check if learning content in the curriculum is taught the students. Therefore, without adequate commitment to the performance of school administrators in their instructional roles, categorized as supervision and curriculum development and innovation, and other aspects of school management, the goals of educational programs towards sustainable national development will continue to be shattered (Watson & Ajekere, 2020). Effective instructional

supervision is enhanced by communicating specific issues through advice, direction and discussion to teachers and students by the principals as supervisors.

Effective Communication as a Panacea for Effective Teachers Service

This is one of the strategies principals or administrators employ to in the course of achieving the stated goals of education conflict may arise which will distort the performance of the staff and the school in general, hence effective communication is employed to settle the issue and promote faster achievement of the goals of education in Nigeria through the performance of the staff. Communication is another critical task area of principals in the management of secondary schools. It involves the process of sharing information, ideas, or attitudes in ways that produce a degree of understanding between two or more people. Communication can also be seen as the ability to convey information or ideas in the simplest form which the recipient can easily understand; and the ability on the other part of the recipient to reciprocate in such a way that he can easily be understood. Communication is said to have been accomplished if the message is interpreted in the same way by the sender and the receiver.

This strategy helps to communicate the aims and objectives of the school system. According to Graham and Lebron cited in Onogri (2009) posited that organizations have employ communication strategy to resolve conflict, this is actualized or achieved by breaking down barriers or resistance among workers and promoting their trust.

Communication is a rational process which involves initiating messages using symbols, signs to express meaning, create similar understanding and influence actions. It is a process or means by which information is shared among individuals through a common system of symbols, signs or behavior (Onyeike, 2013). Appelbaum et al. in Ongori (2009) theorised that groups in trying to actualize a common goal encounter internal and external problems, and one way to resolve or ameliorate the challenge via communication. If these conflict which are most time inevitable in social interaction is not resolved, the performance of the staff will be marred which of course will limit the realization of the goals of the secondary school system. It is necessary to state that no positive action can occur in organization in the absence of effective communication. Principals must develop the right channel that will aid effective communication for efficient functioning and teachers services in the school.

Meyer in Angela (2014) describes effective communication as the best strategy by which conflict can be resolve, because it makes every member understand the kind of communication that could result to problem solving. Communication is important in the daily routine or activities of the school, hence principals manage conflict and promote the achievement of the goals of secondary education by providing the right and adequate information to all in the school. It is imperative to say that the dissemination of accurate and timely information in time of conflict is a veritable tool for conflict management in the school. Effective communication strategy also involves negotiation between two parties involved in a conflict. It could also be a mediatory role undertaken to resolve conflicts situation. In effective communication, there is a promotion of an interaction-based approach through negotiation, enabling the negotiators to see the connection between the situation and the outcome (Donohue, 2003). Donohue (2003) brought forward a cylindrical model of communication where different levels of interaction, motivational sources, intensity and regularity of expression are linked together. Donohue (2003) argued that through understanding how these factors affect each other and how they are functioning jointly is the solution how to approach the negotiation and come to an agreement. In furtherance, Donohue

(2003) expressed the importance of how one should communicate when negotiating. Effective communication according to Donohue (2003) is based on the quality, quantity (only the quantity necessary), relevancy and the behaviour.

The delivery of timely and accurate information before, during and after an incident is an essential component and performance management strategy for teachers' services in secondary schools. Ensuring that the students and staff members, parents, local agencies, the media, and the community have information is the key duty of the school administrator during a crisis (Omeresie, 2014). By ensuring that there is an effective communication in the school system, crises are settled thereby giving room for effective performance of staff for the attainment of the goals of the school system. During crisis, or any critical incident or emergency, the school administrator uses several models of communication to provide warning to the perpetrators of the crisis, disseminate information to all departments, and make notifications. It is a transactional process where people construct meaning and develop expectations about what is happening around them through the exchange of symbols. Constructing meaning involves, people using symbols that is, objects or words that stand for ideas, feelings, intentions, and other objects, to describe their experiences with others. Communication is important in any social setting because it is one of the chief means by which its members work together.

Watson and Ajekere (2020) saw communication to be vital in the relationship between employers and their employees, supervisors and their subordinates in any organization. It is the process through which work gets done by way of giving instruction. Production and regulation purposes include activities aimed at doing the primary work of the organization, such as teaching and learning in schools. They include setting goals and standards, transmitting facts and information, making decisions, leading and influencing others, and assessing outcomes. Innovation purposes include messages about generating new ideas and changing programmes, structures and procedures in the school. Finally, socialization and maintenance purposes of communication affect the participants' self-esteem, interpersonal relationships and motivation to integrate individual goals with the school objectives.

In the school system, communication is vital in the relationships between principals, teachers, students, parents and the public for the achievement of the goals and objectives of education. Effective communication could play an important part in all forms of relationship between the school and the public. This is because it is the process by which ideas, attitudes, and opinions are exchanged between the school and the public. These include school morning assembly, letters and memoranda, staff meetings, school rules and regulations, signs, meeting with school functionaries, and prefectural representatives. If the principal's communication style is unfavorable to teachers working with him, there is the tendency that the teachers would not cooperate with the principal and productivity would be affected. The communication climate created by the school management directly influences the extent to which communication is positive or negative in an organization. Meanwhile, an open or supportive communication climate promotes co-operative working relationship and it is therefore conducive for effective information gathering and transfer. A closed or defective information climate has the opposite effect.

The communication climate influence productivity. An open or supportive communication environment and people are more likely to have a sense of worth and speaks freely without fear of reprisal. This kind of environment created by the school administrator promotes an understanding of what each team member wishes to accomplish and the mutual coexistence towards a common goal of the school (Watson & Ajekere, 2020). They will feel

trusted, secured and confident in their jobs for the organizational growth as a whole towards achieving effective teaching and learning to instill in the learner skills, and aptitudes that are lifelong for sustainable national development. Thus, effective team work, flexibility and a sense of involvement all contribute to and benefit from an open and supportive communication climate operated by the principal in the management of secondary schools. Decisions are communicated to subordinates in the school system for implementation.

Collaboration as a Panacea for Effective Teachers Services

Collaboration in school activities and in decision-making enables complementary skills and experiences which allow them to tackle the problems bothering or facing the organization from different perspective and make practical decisions from the different alternative been set (Ololube et al., 2018). Collaborative decision – making in school system involves the leader or decision – maker (administrator) in helping the staff understand the purpose and nature of the issue, helping the staff focus on working together to solve the challenges faced by the organization and harness their ideas, skills and experiences for the optimal achievement of the goals of the school system.

An important characteristic of collaboration appeared to be its task related focus, including working and reflecting together for job-related purposes (Kelchtermans, 2006). In the case of collaboration, this working together includes the partners in the process doing all their work together as opposed to cooperation in which partners split the work and combine each of their partial results into the final outcomes (Ololube, 2017). Collaboration is seen as different from collegiality as the first tends to refer to the cooperative actions (Kelchtermans, 2006) while the latter focuses on the relationships among colleagues (Bovbjerg, 2006; Kelchtermans, 2006). While collegiality has an inherent positive value as described by Kelchtermans (2006), collegiality is defined as consisting of relationships with colleagues as obligations based on mutual sympathy, solidarity based on an equal work situation, etc. in the case of Bovbjerg (2006). Similarly, Datnow (2011) distinguished between collaborative cultures that support and stimulate spontaneous collaboration and contrived collegiality. While a collaborative culture originates from teachers perceiving collaboration to be valuable, productive, and pleasant, contrived collegiality results from administrative regulation obliging teachers to collaborate. Based upon the assertions above, collaboration can be defined as a joint interaction in the group in all activities that are needed to perform a shared task (Vangrieken, 2015). This concept is not static and uniform but different types of collaboration can occur with varying depths. In a sense collaboration can be seen as an umbrella term, being part of different collaborative concepts.

Twombly (2015) opined that collaborative decision making is the most time consuming style among other styles of decision making, but also create effective administration and goals attainment when done right. She added that most school administrators and organization adopt this style of leadership especially when the subordinates outlined the ways to handle and accomplished the expected, quick, effective and sound follow-up and discussions. Though Tallyfy (2017) argued that most administrators or managers of schools often avoid adopting team or collaborative decision –making style due to the interference of personal agendas and office politics involving arguments and more so he asserts that it is time consuming thereby leading to time wastage in goal attainment. The decision making style can be formal, or informal due to the goal and environment of the team involves. Collaborative decision making require sharing of information to be deliberated on and listening to contributions and suggestions made (Ololube,

2017). However, the school administrator should determine whether or not to adopt collaborative style, considering certain factors. The major factor to consider is time available at his disposal; if time is short, collaborative approach may not be the appropriate decision to adopt as crucial time will be wasted without any meaningful result that will yield to the attainment of the school goals and objectives in educational system. Collaborative style is contingent on others, staff oriented, it is a style of leadership that is considerate, consultative, partite and subordinates-centered (Bass et al., 2008).

A collaborative principal involve his/her subordinates in the organization in decision – making process, the principal initiate discussion, outline problems that needs to be discussed, addressed and keep track of the entire school system rather than selected issues. Though decisions are made through collaborative process of discussion and some form of consensus agreement. The principal who adopt collaborative decision making style has to let go the need for control, power and position for effective running of the school system. The goal of collaborative decision making is the ability to share in decision making which develop trust, respect and relationship between the leader and his subordinates. Goleman and Boyatzis (2008) found that by spending time getting people’s ideas and mutual agreements a collaborative leader build trust and commitment with their subordinates. Bass et al. (2008) in the same vein added that a collaborative administrator elicit ideas from their staff to achieve the right way of getting things accomplished in the organization, thereby been open to constructive critics, and handling mistakes as opportunities to acquire more knowledge and know what to do at the right time.

Sharing issues and details of decision- making is important to involve people to support the decision (Larson, 2017). The school administrator must communicate the reasons for making the decisions effectively and arrive at a high quality decisions that will lead to the success and growth of school system. The school administrator can set up committees within the school system and mandated them to investigate and seek solution over issues bothering the growth of the school thus effective administration.

Less effective school performances have been shown to be those limited only to the system’s structure without considering the human and social elements, such as culture, school climate and human relations. Today, school reform most often includes the aspect of in-school collaboration (Howden & Kopiec, 2002), by promoting professional learning team spirit among staff. In this regard, school principals are increasingly encouraged to facilitate collaboration among their staff (Bouchamma, 2006), as it constitutes the basis of these for achievement of the aims and objectives of the school system. (Eaker et al., 2004). Teacher collaboration is often linked to effective schools and academic achievement (Eaker et al., 2004; Howden & Kopiec, 2002) as well as teacher morale (Bouchamma, 2006). Principal collaborative style of decision making may seem to be inclusive; its dependency on contributions and suggestions of others may not in all cases provide positive results. Ololube (2024) identified that when decision makers (leaders) and subordinates mull over ideas, there is a chance for decisions to become less effective.

This could result to subordinates becoming unstable and confused about the proposed problem even more than they may be before they began deliberating. Some subordinates may even disunite themselves from collective participation.

Collaboration has an impact not only on students and teachers, but also on the school as a whole. In regards to the general objective expressed in Nigeria National Policy on education (FRN, 2014), collaboration between teachers as facilitated by the school administrator enables them to achieve academic goals (Howden & Kopiec, 2002; Linik, 2002; 2001; Tschannen-Moran

et al., 2000). It also helps them collaborate better among themselves (Howden & Kopiec, 2002), as well as affects both their behaviour and their attitude and enables them to experience a greater sense of belonging to the school. Teachers themselves are constantly learning and developing professionally (Spraker, 2003) in terms of, knowledge generated through common discussion, school practices (pedagogical innovations and reforms (Al-Bataineh & Nur-Awaleh, 2000), professional conduct and lasting professional relationships based on respect and reliance, enthusiasm, gratification and satisfaction experienced on a daily basis through interdependence (Tschannen-Moran et al., 2000); and personal growth (with the constant support and feedback of colleagues and non-hierarchical supervision. As a result, the element of collaboration helps schools become more effective and efficient as it influences climate and culture of the school to achieve the goal of secondary education.

Collaborative decision-making is one among the effective decision-making though it is time consuming, in respect to this Goleman et al. (2002) insisted that adopting a collaborative style in time of crisis is wrong. He added that administrator who adopts this style should be flexible when crisis arises in order to calm down situation with prompt authoritative style in the school system, the principal's utilization of decision style in discharging his duties would determine his effective administration and consequently realize the goals of the school system. Ololube (2017) added that school administrators are responsible for the set of ethic or norms that govern the behavior of people in the organization. The type of performance management style adopted will therefore set the time for school, and can be collaborative based on a majority vote after deliberation or dependent on arriving at consensus, with a range of possibilities in between consensus decision making is particularly difficult, it requires everyone to agree before a decision can be made. It takes commitment and patience using this style.

Delegation as a Panacea for Effective Teachers Services

Delegation is the process in which an individual or institution transfers its political or legal authority to a subordinate individual or institution for execution or application. Responding to this, Ololube (2017) defined delegation of authority as the process of giving power or work to somebody else so that the person is responsible for part of what you normally do. In secondary education, it is the act of sharing available functions in the school by the principal to the members of the staff according to their abilities and capabilities towards achieving the goals and objectives of the school.

Delegation of function is very important in secondary school administration. No organization can work without proper delegation of function/ responsibilities. For example, Okafor (2002) asserted that in church, the Pope delegate function to the cardinals, bishops, priests or pastors, pastors to brothers/sisters, catechists and down to laity in the church. In the family, the father as a head delegates functions to the mother, mother to children. In an organization, the manager delegates function to his subordinates. He further stated that delegation implies that a hierarchy of position be created in any organization. This is necessary for achievement of organizational goals which again depends on the proper functioning of the organization. In this capacity, the administrative head of the school in a bid to achieve the goal of secondary education, has to share out some of his functions to competent subordinates so as to facilitate the achievement of the school goals and objectives by assigning tasks to subordinates to perform. This is so because, the school head cannot be found in all places at all times, hence delegation is paramount to achieve success in secondary education. It helps him in the

decentralization of responsibilities of office. The sharing of duties/ tasks within the school and the grouping of duties into departments with group heads leads to easier management. Since delegation can take place in all levels of management, departmental heads themselves may become involved in delegation. In management studies delegation of function/responsibilities has become a word in vogue in recent years. It is management practice professed by most managers and administrators but least practiced by them (Ololube, 2024).

Delegation of function has been variously defined by different writers/authors. This implies that in an organization, there is always an executive head that is responsible for sharing functions or duties among his subordinate staff. In the school system for instance, the principal is the head who has a number of subordinate staff in both the academic and administrative cadre, among whom he shares responsibilities for the smooth running of the school. Then the principal takes into account the staff's hierarchy of positions and competences while delegating functions in order to guarantee optimal performance of the staffs. A principal as an executive head cannot possibly deal effectively with all tasks which other people may have the time and energy to do. In the view of Akubue (2002), delegation of functions can be explained as a process whereby a super-ordinate (leader) vests decision making discretion on a subordinate and make it possible for them to use their judgment... just as no one person in an enterprise can do all the tasks necessary for the accomplishment of group purpose. So it is impossible as an enterprise grows for one person to exercise authority for making decision.

He further asserted that some members of your staff may become unhappy if you do not entrust them with some responsibilities which they are eager and ready to carry. You may strain your relationship with them. Obviously, one definite effect of not delegating responsibilities will be poor organizational inefficiency and ultimate failure to achieve the major goals of the institution. Therefore, you will see the institution not as your own but as an organization which every member of staff is playing some vital role and in which one of your main duties is the coordination and supervision of the various functions. You establish a chain of command to make things work harmoniously and efficiently. Delegation is a process by which managers, such as school heads, transfer part of their authority to subordinates for the performance of certain tasks and responsibilities”.

Delegation of function is not the assignment of unpleasant and boring task that a superior wishes to avoid, but rather he believe that it is the assignment of the part of the superior responsibilities and it may be those parts in which the subordinate is an expert. The implication of all these is that delegation creates an additional obligation on the part of the delegate without diminishing the responsibility of the superior (Ololube, 2024). The subordinate shares in higher responsibilities while still ensuring effective and efficient performance. This is therefore the way superior provide for the maximum performance of their duties and it is an essential way for the establishment of an effective administrative structure. This is because the attainment of educational goal is a function of the cumulative inter play of the forces (internal and external) influencing the school system. Principals' expertise is known to effectively and diligently influence individual and collective forces to achieve the specified goals of education by delegating responsibilities to subordinates that are most suitable for a particular responsibility in line with expected outcomes.

In the opinion of Okonkwo (1998) as cited in Ugwu (2009) experience has confirmed that delegation of responsibilities is one of the major factors contributing to good principal, better performance and staff relations. Involvement of staff in decision-making which has been shown to be related to delegation of responsibilities, also promotes good principal and staff relations for

the attainment of education goals. Most staff would be unhappy if they are not entrusted with any responsibilities and the denial of responsibility to staff will strain their relationship with the principal. He further asserted that delegation of duties based on expertise practice to staff enables them not only to put in their best but also expose their talents, because in some cases, the heads and staff sit together and formulate school internal policies to satisfy the curiosity of internal happenings. Okonkwo (1998) in Ugwu (2009) also noted that teachers are proud whenever they are involved in school affairs, more importantly those that have to do with delegation and decision making. The head's involvement of subordinates in both delegation of responsibility and decision-making is an indication that he is applying the principles of democratic leadership and so de-emphasizing autocratic leadership which many authors have rejected as an improper way of administering schools. It is expected that in our school system, heads should delegate duties to staff so as to ensure democratic participation, group effort among staff which will encourage administrative co-operation.

Constraints of Performance Management Strategies

Despite considerable enthusiasm generated by performance management through its strategies, many administrators may find it difficult to implement this concept in the secondary schools. Studies that are specifically concerned with the implementation of performance management indicate challenges and constraints faced by school managers in this respect. Ololube (2017) found that the implementation of performance management is constrained by institutional and capacity problems such as culture, institutional fragmentation, public support and inept leadership. There are a number of reasons why performance management strategies can be ineffective at the public secondary school setting and this according to Ezeonu and Akani (2010) includes:

- **Lack of capacity:** Most supervisors, principals and teachers are not acquainted with performance management strategies and how they can be applied to achieve educational goals. This is because there is no training before they go into the practice. A good number of supervisors, principals and teachers are not well informed about their responsibilities due to lack of in-service training and workshops. Supervisors can fall back to using the faultfinding techniques because he or she is not knowledgeable about the modern methods and techniques that can be applied to enhance performance of their staff.
- **Inadequate provision of financial and material resources:** School administrators cannot carry out their duties effectively when there are inadequate facilities such as office equipment, furniture, vehicles etc. Most schools are still in dilapidated buildings and offices. In such places keeping of most school records becomes a difficult task and enforcing certain rules and regulations become difficult. How can you for example effectively monitor late-coming without an attendance register? Funding is also a major challenge in the educational system.
- **Not recognizing and rewarding performance:** School supervisors, principals and teachers are poorly remunerated. They are not commensurately motivated and rewarded for the jobs they do and so they engage in other gainful activities which distract them from their main duties. Supervisors look out for gratification in exchange for a good report being given on schools. Teachers are not promoted as at when due, even when promoted, there is no financial benefit attached. There is no commendation for high performers. This

results to low morale and consequently poor performance and poor educational achievements in our schools.

- Irregular and delay in payment of salaries: This also constitutes a challenge to performance management. School administrators are most times not paid as at when due and this can lead to low performance as reward stands out as a motivation to performance and goal attainment.
- Type of leadership styles: Leadership style in a school affects the behavior staff either negatively or positively. A principal's leadership style be it democratic, autocratic, or laissez faire - could lead to high morale or low morale of the members of staff which invariably affect their performance and teachers services in the school. A supervisor or principal who imbibes favouritism as a style for example, is bound to demoralize hardworking members of staff and dampen their performance and ability to attainment set goal.

CONCLUSION

An administration of performance management strategies required the school administrator to be proficient in his or her administrative duties in addition with the possession of sound knowledge. This implies that his or her experience should exceed the vision, knowledge and skills of those under the purview of his/her responsibility. Presently, principals and other administrative staff in schools are recruited from pool of teachers who have little or no knowledge of performance management and therefore are unable to apply performance management strategies for effective teachers' services. Their selection is based on their possession of degrees and seniority with no upgrade of their managerial skills. Thus, they do not adequately inspect, monitor, supervise, evaluate and measure the performance of individual staff and students for enhancement of positive teachers' services and students' achievement respectively.

Suggestions

From the above discussions, the following suggestions are made:

- The administrators of various schools should always as a matter of effectiveness, supervise the teachers to ensure they are quickened to deliver their services in a competent manner.
- Collaboration performance management strategy should be adopted to build the team spirit among teachers for effective cooperation and performances in secondary schools.
- In matters of crises, effective communication should be employed to settle the issue and unite the staff for the attainment of the goals of education.
- Principals of various secondary schools are advised to implore their intuition on the performance management strategy to apply in order to achieve maximum result.
- Staff appraisal should often be conducted to find out the competencies of teachers and proffer solution accordingly.
- The administrators are advised to consider the skills and experience of the staff to be delegated a function, else the objective of the delegation will be forfeited. The staff should be trained and monitored before delegation can take place.

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